

TUBULOINTERSTITIAL INFLAMMATORY KIDNEY DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Summary.

This review is considered as a collection of acute and chronic tubulointerstitial inflammatory diseases of the kidneys (TIDK), characterized by the involvement in the pathological process of all structures of the nephron. One of the urgent problems of modern medicine is kidney damage in rheumatoid arthritis. The issues of prevalence of tubulointerstitial inflammatory diseases of the kidneys, etiology, pathogenesis, clinical manifestations and treatment are considered. The kidneys are affected in rheumatoid arthritis more often than it is diagnosed. As a result, early diagnosis of kidney damage in patients with rheumatoid arthritis has an important clinical and prognostic value. In rheumatoid arthritis, the occurrence of chronic kidney disease depends primarily on the duration of the disease and the nature of the inflammatory process. These data are fully confirmed at the present time. The problem of kidney damage in rheumatoid arthritis is poorly understood and requires further research.

Key words.

rheumatoid arthritis, tubulointerstitial kidney disease, diagnosis, treatment.

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is an autoimmune inflammatory rheumatic disease of unknown etiology that has a chronic course and affects more than one joint and system [1,10].

Rheumatoid arthritis is not just a disease that causes joint damage. Rheumatoid arthritis has a number of mechanisms that can also cause damage to other organs. Rheumatoid arthritis can cause pain, joint swelling, loss of function, and loss of function in individuals. Rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic disease that can affect not only physical health, but also psychological and social functions [2,12,13]. Therefore, it includes a treatment plan that includes both treatment and social support. Patients with rheumatoid arthritis face problems such as pain, swelling of the joints and inability to continue their daily and professional life. In addition, they need to cope with the side effects of the treatment they receive. These side effects can be listed as important side effects such as tuberculosis, non-Hodking's lymphoma, infections of the respiratory system such as pneumonia,

dermatological problems, gastrointestinal problems such as nausea and vomiting. These side effects cause people to stop treatment and even withdraw from treatment [3,7,8,9].

Many researchers noted that in RA patients the development of CKD and the severity of its manifestations are determined by the duration and activity of the underlying disease, age, the presence of arterial hypertension (AH), lipid metabolism disorders and hyperglycemia [15].

Tubulointerstitial inflammatory diseases of the kidneys (ICD 10): N10 acute tubulointerstitial nephritis (TIN): infectious (pyelonephritis); N11 chronic TIN: infectious (pyelonephritis); N13 obstructive and refluxuopathy; N14 tubulointerstitial and tubular lesions caused by drugs and heavy metals; N16 tubulointerstitial lesions of the kidneys in other diseases. Tubulointerstitial diseases are much more common than glomerular diseases - 4.6% versus 0.46% (according to autopsy data). The frequency varies in different regions and social environments. Autopsy: 1.9% (1.7% acute TIN, 0.2% chronic TIN). The bulk of the patients TIVZP are suffering from diffuse bacterial forms [4.]. Relatively common urinary tract infection (as an independent form of the disease). Suggested structure of the TIVZP:

I. Acute TIN. A. Diffuse (drug and infectious (apostematous nephritis, pyelonephritis) B. Focal (reflux nephropathy, ischemic).

II. Chronic TIN, A. diffuse (toxic, immune (including secondary); B. focal (pyelonephritis).

III. Tubulointerstitial component of primary glomerular, vascular diseases kidneys.

TUBULOINTERSTITIAL NEPHRITE

This is a multifactorial (but not bacterial) diffuse kidney disease with a predominant involvement of tubulointerstitial tissue, distinct from glomerulonephritis (GN) and pyelonephritis. It is distinguished from GN by a primary lesion of the tubulointerstitial tissue with secondary involvement of the glomeruli in the process. From pyelonephritis - diffuse nature of the process and abacterial nature. Two forms are considered - acute (ATIN) and chronic (CTIN). These are different diseases. The problem of acute drug-induced kidney injury goes beyond ATIN. The latter include acute tubular necrosis, functional (electrolyte-hemodynamic) renal failure, acute interstitial nephritis proper, acute drug-induced GN, necrotizing angiitis of the vessels of the kidneys, bilateral cortical necrosis, nutricanal obstruction (crystals of urates, sulfonamides), necrosis of the renal papillae.

ACUTE TUBULOINTERSTITIAL NEPHRITIS

ATIN is, in fact, neoliguric reversible acute renal failure, more often of an allergic nature. Etiology. The most common cause of ATIN is drug exposure, drugs, primarily antibiotics, especially penicillin and its semi-synthetic derivatives (ampicillin, methicillin), gentamicin; then sulfonamides, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs): indomethacin, brufen, fenoprofen, barbiturates, cimetidine, captopril, radiopaque agents, as well as sera and vaccines.

Pathogenesis. The main pathophysiological mechanisms of drug nephropathy can be reduced to 5 options.

1. An excessive pharmacological effect that led to impaired renal function, drug poisoning (for example, with excessive use of a diuretic, hypotension occurs, renal failure, alkalosis, hypokalemia is possible).

2. The peculiarity of nephrohormonal, vasoactive and transport mechanisms in the kidneys (water retention and hyponatremia may occur when using hypoglycemic agents).

3. Immunological renal damage (drug-induced vasculitis, typical variants of ATIN).

4. Direct tubular damage and toxicity (with the appointment of aminoglycosides, acute renal failure develops, losses of K⁺ and Mg²⁺).

5. Decreased renal perfusion.

Clinical manifestations. Typically acute onset in the first days (hours). The triad is characteristic: fever, eosinophilia, impaired renal function. There is a urinary syndrome: hematuria, erythrocyte casts may appear, sterile leukocyturia, moderate proteinuria, eosinophiluria. Usually, with timely diagnosis of ATIN and timely treatment, creatinemia, the main criterion for the severity of the disease, normalizes within 1–2 weeks. Polyuria, isosthenuria, hypostenuria, and lean urinary syndrome may last longer. Systemic manifestations of ATIN are also possible. So, in case of "aminoglycoside" etiology, ATIN is often combined with damage to the inner ear with hearing loss. Renal failure increases at a relatively slow pace, usually reversible after discontinuation of the drug. Unexpressed lumbodynia is possible. ATIN - more often a favorable current disease.

Treatment. 80% of patients with ATIN do not need special therapy. The first rule is to cancel all previous treatment. With polyuria, when the patient excretes 2-4 liters of urine per day, electrolyte disturbances may develop. And the severity of the patient's condition is practically determined not by creatinemia (uremic intoxication, in fact, does not have time to develop), but by severe dyselectrolytemia. Severe muscle weakness, symptoms of heart failure due to

electrolyte disorders, primarily hypokalemia. Along with it, hyponatremia develops. These violations need to be corrected in a timely manner.

If the disease is severe and one has to deal with renal failure itself, then it is advisable to use desensitizing therapy, ranging from “small” (antihistamines) to glucocorticosteroids (GCS).

In obstructive uropathy caused by blockage of the tubules by uric acid, the optimal therapeutic measure is the use of allopurinol, a xanthine oxide inhibitor. Additional measures are abundant fluid intake and alkalization of urine with sodium bicarbonate. If, despite all these measures, progressive renal failure develops, then, as a rule, hemodialysis is effective in removing uric acid. In most cases, thanks to the latter, diuresis will recover within a few days.

CHRONIC TUBULOINTERSTITIAL NEPHRITIS

CTIN is a multifactorial abacterial diffuse inflammatory and/or metabolic kidney disease with a predominant lesion of tubulointerstitial tissue.

Etiology. The concept of etiology in this case is conditional, known forms (analgesic, lead, gouty and some other nephropathies) are described as independent diseases.

Apparently, any drug (xenobiotic) can be a potential etiological factor.

Pathogenesis. The development of drug nephropathy is based on hypersensitivity to certain drugs (predestination, "risk factor"), which develops against the background of congenital (anomalies) or acquired (trauma, kidney disease) disorders, leading to hemodynamic disorders in the kidney. Sensitization is characterized by increased production of IgE, release of anaphylaxis mediators. The prostaglandin (PG) system is involved in the process, which even more disrupts the already altered microcirculation with the development of edema and damage to the interstitium. Only in isolated cases, the use of common drugs causes a direct toxic effect with the development of kidney damage without an allergic component. A factor that predetermines the vulnerability of the kidneys may be a congenital defect of the renal tissue, manifested by overt or latent hereditary nephropathy. It is based on various genetic defects, which determines the great variability of clinical and morphological manifestations. Hereditary nephropathies include some renal dysplasia, accounting for about 20% of their number.

Morphological changes. The extreme expression of drug nephropathy is necrosis of the papillary zone or medulla. Exudative inflammatory and degenerative lesions of the medulla, most often there is a pronounced sclerosis of these zones. The cortical substance associated with preserved papillae is not changed. The

tubules are obliterated, lose contact with the cup, as a result, the entire nephron atrophies, the tubules shrink, interstitial fibrosis occurs, and the glomeruli shrink ischemically. If the papillae that have undergone necrosis are separated, then the cavity can epithelialize and some tubules will get access to the cup. In these cases, the glomeruli and tubules retain their function and often hypertrophy.

Clinical manifestations. The most affected age is 30–40 years of age. For a long time, a latent course is possible, there may be mildly pronounced asthenovegetative disorders, urinary syndrome. Nephrotic and hypertensive syndromes are rare. An early decrease in the concentrating function of the kidneys is possible. Changed sensitivity to various drugs is revealed. The low frequency of PN makes this disease rarely diagnosed. Given the variety of forms of CTIN, we can talk about some specific features of the clinic of these forms.

So, with analgesic nephropathy, along with clinical, certain social characteristics are described. Older persons (mean age 60 ± 10 years), predominantly women who abuse smoking, often suffer from pain of various localization. Clinically, various concomitant diseases are often detected: coronary artery disease, heart rhythm disturbances, peptic ulcer, anemia, hyperlipoproteinemia.

Compared with other forms of CTIN, analgesic nephropathy is more severe. Frequent complaints of headache and heavy use of analgesics. For such patients, the abuse of drugs other than analgesics is also characteristic.

Frequent mental disorders. Papillary necrosis occurs in more than 50% of patients with analgesic nephropathy. The frequency of pyuria, usually sterile, more than 60%, hypertension - 50%, malignant hypertension is rare, proteinuria is also rare. More often than in 50% of cases, anemia develops, atherosclerosis progresses faster. With the so-called furosemide CTIN, there are more pronounced electrolyte disorders and a greater likelihood of tubular acidosis than with other forms of CTIN [5]. Cadmium nephropathies can be associated with industrial pollution, first described in Japan, manifested mainly by proximal tubular dystrophy, clinically resemble the picture of parathyroid hormone hyperproduction: urinary stones, osteoporosis, osteomalacia, false fractures, an increase in alkaline phosphatase (AP) activity in the blood. Chronic cadmium nephropathy may result in PN. In severe cases of cadmium intoxication, gastritis, enteritis, anemia, pulmonary emphysema, and pulmonary hypertension develop.

Sandimmune nephropathy [6,14]. Cyclosporin A (CsA, sandimmun) has a pronounced nephrotoxicity, which develops both in the transplanted kidney and in the recipient's own kidneys during heart, liver, etc. transplantation. At high doses

of Sandimmun (10–15 mg/kg) after heart or liver transplantation, Sandimmune Nephropathy results in terminal uremia at year 7–8 of transplantation in every 10th recipient; the development of sandimmune nephropathy is much less common when using low doses of the drug - 5 mg / kg. The mechanisms of chronic nephrotoxicity of Sandimmun include narrowing of the afferent arteriole, induction of NO-dependent apoptosis of tubular epithelial cells and interstitial fibrosis, stimulation of the synthesis of transforming growth factor, and a direct damaging effect on the vascular endothelium of the kidneys and platelet receptors. Lead nephropathy is latent for a long time. In 90% of lead excretion in the urine is almost twice the normal. In half of them, the glomerular filtration rate is reduced (less than 90 ml/min). There are data confirming the immune nature of lead nephropathy. Of the individuals who had lead nephropathy and hypertension, half developed renal failure within 1 year, in the control group (without hypertension) such rapid progression was not observed. CTIN is competent in gout, since hyperuricemia has an undoubted nephrotoxicity. This is proved by the reversibility of the process with successful therapy of gout with allopurinol and with the termination of treatment - the development of renal failure. A similar clinical picture may also occur in connection with gout, but directly due to pyelonephritis, ureteral and intratubular obstruction.

Diagnostics. CTIN as an independent drug disease must meet the following clinical, laboratory and morphological criteria: the presence of congenital dysplasia of the renal tissue or (rarely) acquired damage to the latter (injuries, possibly diseases); increased (congenital and acquired) sensitivity to drugs, which determines allergic reactions of an immediate or delayed type; a significant increase in the content of IgE; clinical, laboratory and morphological signs of diffuse non-destructive tubulointerstitial inflammation. Let us designate some typical manifestations [6.]: a combination of persistent aseptic leukocyturia with episodes of renal colic, accompanied by gross hematuria, in the absence of nephrolithiasis; polyuria, a decrease in the size of the kidneys, anemia that does not correspond to the severity of CRF. Ultrasound diagnostics (USD) of the kidneys, even in the stages of advanced renal failure, can reveal a typical pattern of garlands of calcified papillae around the renal sinus. Papillary changes range from edema to defects of varying severity. Necrotized papillae may remain in place and calcify or rupture into the renal parenchyma, appearing radiographically as filling defects. Computed tomography (CT) reveals a decrease in the size of both kidneys in combination with uneven contours or calcification of the papillae. CT is the most adequate diagnostic method, since it allows to determine the most pathognomonic sign of the disease -

calcification of the renal papillae. Kidney biopsy is uninformative and is indicated only if there are signs of damage to the glomeruli or blood vessels. Non-renal changes are characteristic of medicinal CTIN. Naturally, they are different for different forms of drug disease. The most typical lesions of the gastrointestinal tract (recurrent stomatitis, peptic ulcer of the stomach); hematological syndrome (iron deficiency, hemolytic and macrocytic anemia, splenomegaly). Possible neuropsychiatric disorders, observed in 80-90% of patients and manifested by headache, migraine, personality disorders, psychosis. At the same time, the abuse of laxatives, psychotropic drugs, alcohol, and smoking is often noted; pigmentation of the skin of patients (pale yellow color) due to the presence in the skin of a substance close to lipofuscin, which can increase with uremia and the development of a salt-losing state; premature aging.

Treatment. First of all, it is necessary to eliminate the cause of the disease. If we are talking about the abuse of drugs, then you need to stop taking them. In other cases, treatment is symptomatic. Unfortunately, there are no methods of pathogenetic treatment yet. In all situations with the presence of risk factors for drug-induced kidney injury, analgesic mixtures should be prohibited. Patients who have previously developed AKI after taking analgesics or NSAIDs should not be given these drugs. In the event of an emergency, the appointment of an analgesic

paracetamol, which has the least nephrotoxicity, can be considered the drug of choice. Keeping in mind that long-term use of diuretics can cause changes in the renal tissue, you should not resort to their long-term administration.

For the prevention of Sandimmun nephrotoxicity, small and medium doses of the drug are recommended with mandatory monitoring of its concentration in the blood. Calcium antagonists are also effective. They correct "sandimmune" hypertension and renal vasoconstriction, have a positive effect on the function of T-lymphocytes and the pharmacodynamics of sandimmune. The use of verapamil, diltiazem, amlodipine can reduce the daily dose of Sandimmun.

Prognosis and outcomes: the prognosis of the disease depends on the morphological variant of glomerulonephritis, the frequency of exacerbations, the development of chronic renal failure. Patients are under medical supervision in one of the nephrological centers of the city with control of laboratory and functional parameters, if necessary - hospitalization.

Primary prevention consists in the timely treatment of streptococcal infection to prevent the development of acute glomerulonephritis, in the case of chronic glomerulonephritis, the prevention of early development of complications (in particular, chronic renal failure) [11].

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